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Stakeholder and Community Engagement in Advancing Ireland's Open Repository Landscape

A Case Study

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<https://www.universityofgalway.ie/openrepositories>

Overview

The National Open Access Repositories project presents a comprehensive **community-focused approach** for enhancing Ireland's open repositories through extensive stakeholder engagement. The project, funded by the National Open Research Forum (NORF), emphasises collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including universities, research performing organisations (RPOs), and governmental bodies, to overcome challenges related to **Green open access**, infrastructure development, resourcing, and metadata quality.

The project's work highlights key challenges such as insufficient funding and investment, diverse repository practices, and metadata inconsistencies. Through consultations, surveys, self-assessment and interviews, stakeholders across academia, government, and the research community were actively involved in shaping the project's recommendations in *Advancing Ireland's Open Repository Landscape: A Strategic Roadmap (2024)* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810233>.

Stakeholder Engagement

The project team employed mixed methodologies, including surveys, self-assessments, and interviews, to engage with institutional partners and key stakeholders. Open dialogues were held with institutional and repository representatives to address repository-specific issues. This engagement was crucial in understanding the varied needs, limitations and opportunities across different research environments.

Stakeholder engagement was conducted nationally and internationally. Through consultations with global leaders, such as COAR (Confederation of Open Access Repositories) and OpenAIRE, the project integrated global best practices into the evolving national strategy. This alignment was instrumental in positioning Irish repositories for better global visibility and ensuring compliance with open research mandates.

The project also focused on cross-sector engagement, ensuring inclusivity by engaging a wide range of RPOs, including educational and governmental repositories in its engagement work. Cross-sectoral collaboration helped identify common challenges, such as the need for improved metadata practices and repository visibility, while ensuring that solutions would be adaptable across different types of institutions. At the same time, the project engaged other NORF-funded projects under the same funding call, notably the **National Open Access Monitor**. Ensuring the exchange of information between projects allowed a coordinated approach that persists today.

Community-driven feedback was essential to the ongoing success of the project. Repository managers and strategists were actively involved in providing input to the national repository strategy during semi-structured interviews. These discussions revealed critical insights into repository challenges, including resourcing, system updates, and compliance issues, which were incorporated into the project's recommendations. This approach ensured that community-driven perspectives shaped the overall roadmap, emphasising a bottom-up, grassroots engagement strategy.

Interviews and Dialogues: A Community-Driven Approach

To ensure the strategic roadmap was grounded in real-world experiences, the project team conducted interviews with a diverse group of repository managers and strategists. These interviews focused on the **technical and strategic challenges** faced by Irish open repositories, particularly in areas such as metadata quality, repository working practices, and alignment with international guidelines like OpenAIRE and Plan S.

Stakeholders consistently highlighted challenges related to metadata inconsistencies, which created barriers to repository interoperability and discoverability. There was a general consensus on the need for a national framework to standardise metadata across repositories, ensuring compliance.

Many repository managers also pointed out the chronic shortage of skilled personnel dedicated to maintaining and developing repositories. Many institutions reported significant resource constraints, with some operating with less than one full-time equivalent (FTE) staff member dedicated to their repository. Repository managers stressed the need for national support to address technical and managerial skills gaps. This lack of dedicated personnel prevents these repositories from fully engaging with the broader open research agenda. The Roadmap addresses this issue by proposing **training programs and capacity-building workshops** aimed at upskilling repository managers and technical staff.

Outcomes

As a direct result of these engagements, the Roadmap recommended nationwide training programs and the establishment of a community of practice to foster knowledge-sharing and peer support among repository managers. This **collaborative, community-focused model** would help smaller repositories and those struggling with limited resources share the knowhow required to maintain open access standards, particularly in metadata management and system updates.

Without adequate resources, repositories risk falling behind in adopting new technologies and adhering to evolving open access mandates. Stakeholders stressed the critical role repositories play in preserving diverse scholarly outputs and providing equitable access to research. However, many expressed concern about the over-reliance on commercial publishing platforms, which could undermine the long-term sustainability of open access repositories.

The findings from these interviews were instrumental in shaping the strategic recommendations in the roadmap, particularly in areas such as training and capacity building, where stakeholders saw a critical need for support.

Building a National Open Repository Community

One of the major successes of the stakeholder engagement process was the formation of a burgeoning national community around open repositories. The project team worked to foster a sense of collective ownership over the roadmap's goals, ensuring that all stakeholders felt that their contributions were valued.

The idea of a repository network emerged from this process, where participants expressed a desire for ongoing collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and peer support. This network would serve as a professional community where repository managers and staff could share updates on repository technologies, discuss policy changes, and collectively troubleshoot challenges. The project has since developed a member network for repository staff and RPOs in Ireland called **Open Repositories Ireland (ORI)**, to be launched in Q4 2024.

ORI is a new membership organisation dedicated to advancing open research practices and repository services across Ireland. It provides a collaborative platform for open repository managers and practitioners to share knowledge, develop best practices, and advocate for open science principles within the Irish research community, supported by their institutional research ecosystems. ORI focuses on promoting, supporting, and developing open repositories through networking, training, and advocacy. By joining ORI, institutions will contribute to shaping the future of Green open research in Ireland and achieving the goal of 100% open access by 2030.

By building this community, the roadmap aims to ensure that the progress made through stakeholder engagement continues long after the initial project phase. The professional networks created during the project will help ensure that repository managers and strategists remain connected, engaged, and aligned with the national vision for open access.

Investing in Community Metadata to Enrich the Research Ecosystem

In summer 2024, based on the 2023 consultation phase, the project launched a pilot to align Ireland's open repositories with OpenAIRE v4 guidelines. Four institutions – Atlantic Technological University (ATU), University of Galway, Marine Institute, and Health Service Executive (HSE) – joined the pilot, representing two distinct use cases. One of the necessary steps was upgrading DSpace installations to meet compliance standards. ATU and the University of Galway also focused on integrating their repositories with Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) to streamline workflows and enhance metadata quality. The pilot is leading to the establishment of guidelines for OpenAIRE compliance, offering repository managers recommendations on handling legacy data and mapping DSpace metadata fields.

Looking ahead, the four pilot repositories are expected to achieve full alignment with OpenAIRE v4 guidelines by the end of 2024. The community of repository managers will play a proactive role in managing and evolving the guidelines as technology and standards change. The goal is to expand these efforts nationally to bring all additional repositories into alignment with OpenAIRE standards, fostering **a sustainable, connected open repository network.**

A Stakeholder-Centred Roadmap

Stakeholder and community engagement efforts were crucial to developing the Roadmap. Through an inclusive and collaborative approach, the project not only addressed the immediate challenges facing Irish repositories but also laid the groundwork for **a future-oriented, globally aligned open repository ecosystem**. By harnessing the collective expertise of stakeholders, the Roadmap and ongoing community efforts including the pilot and the launch of ORI ensures that Ireland is well-positioned to lead in open scholarly communication and innovation on the international stage.

By actively involving stakeholders at every stage – from survey participation to in-depth interviews and consultations – the project team ensured that the project’s outputs addressed real-world challenges and reflected the needs of the repository community. Through sustained engagement and community-driven solutions, this work lays the foundation for a more resilient, sustainable, and interconnected open repository network in Ireland, ensuring that it aligns with global best practices and contributes to a vibrant open research ecosystem.

This case study illustrates the importance of **inclusive, data-driven stakeholder engagement** in developing strategic initiatives for national infrastructure projects. By prioritising collaboration and community input, the project’s outputs not only address the technical and operational challenges faced by Irish repositories but also fosters a culture of shared responsibility and continuous improvement across the open access landscape.